

Scenario planning workshop on risks to Natural Capital - Deliverable 3.3

KJHI-D5-2 Climate Change Risks to Natural Capital

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Highlights

What were we trying to find out?

We set out to explore stakeholders' perceptions of the risks posed to natural capital by climate change and other factors, as well as potential response options, using scenario planning techniques with a horizon of 2050.

What did we do?

We developed three scenario narratives, together with stakeholders involved in natural capital and its management, depicting the potential future development of natural capital and the drivers that affect it. We then used these scenario narratives to help explore risks and opportunities for natural capital that could emerge in the context of each different scenario, and then deliberating on and appraising responses to these. We also assessed wildfire risk, as a specific example of a risk posed to natural capital, as well as potential responses to wildfire incidence in each of the scenarios.

What did we learn?

This group of stakeholders was able to identify a range of risks, using the scenarios. These were risks associated with climatic extremes, compounded by degradation of natural capital, resulting in a loss of resilience, and potentially large-scale damage and degradation of natural capital and associated values. Suggested opportunities and responses to these risks focused on the importance of diversification (both in terms of genetic diversity in ecosystems, and deployment of diverse management strategies), as well as on well-planned integration of different management approaches, knowledge exchange across scales, and coherence of natural capital governance. The knowledge and connectedness of rural communities to the landscape were considered important resources for supporting the resilience of natural capital.

What happens now?

We will elaborate analysis of the data collected through the workshop, and use this to inform development of tools, such as risk maps, and contribute to development of a 'risk and opportunities assessment framework', for supporting decision-making about risks to natural capital.

Executive summary

This report is part of research ongoing in Work Package 3 of the Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital project, contributing to the Scottish Government's Strategic Research Programme (2022-2027). The objective of the work reported here was to explore stakeholders' perceptions of future risks posed to woodland and peatland natural capital in Scotland, as well as opportunities and responses to risk. To do this, we developed scenarios, together with stakeholders involved in natural capital and its management, and combined them with climate models produced by the [James Hutton Institute Climate Data Visualisation](#). We then used these scenarios in an online workshop on 11th March 2024 with 20 stakeholders from the realms of policy, research, community development, forestry, agriculture, and land management, to prompt the stakeholders to explore risks, opportunities and responses to them in different scenarios.

Three scenarios were developed, one based on perceived 'positive' assumptions about the future development of natural capital, the second based on perceived 'business as usual' assumptions, and the third based on perceived 'negative' assumptions. Participants in the workshop were split into three groups, each representing a range of stakeholder perspectives, and each group was given one of the three scenarios to work with. The participants were asked to imagine they were living in their group's scenario, and were then facilitated through two activities that involved populating tables on a virtual collaboration platform, Miro. Specifically, participants were asked to discuss and identify risks and opportunities for natural capital in their scenario, the potential chains of impacts these could have, potential responses to each risk and opportunity, as well as the likelihood and severity of each one. Then, in the second activity, participants were asked to consider wildfire as a specific example of a risk, its impacts, and responses to it.

This group of participants identified and considered a wide range of risks, opportunities, and associated responses across the three scenarios, suggesting the use of different scenarios can be useful for facilitating assessments of future risk. However, the process would have been enriched by more time and in-person interactions. The results from workshop discussions revealed that risks associated with climatic extremes were expected to be compounded by degradation of ecosystems, increasing the likelihood and severity of wildfire, as well as other risks such as flooding, storms, and pests and diseases. This could result in large-scale damage and destruction of natural capital and decline of the values associated with it. The detrimental effects of such risks for rural communities were also highlighted, including population decline and associated loss of knowledge and community values. However, there were potential opportunities identified, associated with increased investment through natural capital schemes, and increased technological development for monitoring.

In terms of responses to these risks, diversification, in terms of genetic diversity in nature, as well as in terms of what is included in natural capital markets, and the funding used to support natural capital schemes, was considered important to bolster resilience and take advantage of opportunities for natural capital. Taking an integrated approach to managing natural capital was considered critical to the success of responses to risks and opportunities. This includes integration of appropriate options for managing different aspects of the landscape, engagement and knowledge exchange across scales, and well-planned, coherent policy and legal frameworks. The knowledge, experience, and connectedness of rural communities to the landscape are both considered vital resources for supporting the resilience of natural capital, but are themselves threatened by the risks identified herein. Engagement and empowerment of local communities may therefore be invaluable in ensuring the resilience of natural capital to present and future risks.

Scenario planning workshop on risks to Natural Capital

1. Introduction

This report describes a workshop, conducted in fulfilment of Deliverable 3.3 of Work Package 3, on the project 'Climate Change Risks to Natural Capital' (Project KJHI-D5-2 in the Scottish Government's Strategic Research Programme (2022-2027)). Work Package 3 of the Climate Change Risks to Natural Capital project aims to conduct stakeholder engagement, including via the use of 'scenario planning', to explore perceptions and behaviours towards risk and co-construct novel mitigation strategies, including revised risk communication approaches. This workshop was therefore intended to explore stakeholders' perceptions of the risks posed to natural capital by climate change and other factors, with a horizon of 2050.

We conducted this workshop as the second of two complementary workshops, organised in collaboration with another project on the Strategic Research Programme – KJHI-D5-1 'Bringing in participatory approaches to widen the scope of natural capital valuation'. Taken together, these two workshops explored the potential future development of natural capital, including the values associated with it, the drivers, risks and opportunities, and uncertainties that affect it, and how it may effectively be managed. The workshops were designed around a 'participatory scenario planning' process with stakeholders involved in natural capital management. Participatory scenario planning (PSP) involves groups of people developing and analysing a set of alternative 'scenarios' that describe plausible future conditions of a particular subject (in this case, natural capital in Scotland), through discussion and deliberation (Bennett et al., 2016). PSP has been used prolifically in research and practical planning that focus on social-ecological systems, (Oteros-Rozas et al., 2015) including for understanding, valuing and managing ecosystem services and natural capital (Burdon et al., 2022; Nijnik and Miller, 2017). The *process* of developing and analysing scenarios in groups is useful for engaging stakeholders, exploring their attitudes and perceptions on a subject, facilitating learning, and identifying gaps in knowledge (Johnson et al., 2012; Oteros-Rozas et al., 2015; Poskitt et al., 2021). PSP is also renowned for helping people understand and respond to uncertainties, risks and opportunities (Amer et al., 2013).

The first workshop concentrated on developing scenario narratives regarding the drivers of change, relationships, feedbacks, trade-offs and uncertainties that could affect natural capital, as well as the values associated with it, and its future development. These scenario narratives were then used in this second workshop to help explore risks and opportunities for the condition of natural capital. This involved identifying risks and opportunities that could emerge in the context of each different

scenario, and then deliberating on and appraising responses to these. It also included assessing wildfire risk, as a specific example of a risk posed to natural capital, as well as potential responses to wildfire incidence in each of the scenarios.

Considering the broad focus of this research on natural capital, its future development, and the potential risks posed to it, at the Scottish national level, it was important to include stakeholders who could provide high-level information and expertise from a range of perspectives. We therefore invited stakeholders who represented the perspectives of: policy, environmental agencies, agroforestry, agriculture, land management, research and community development organisations. To focus discussions about natural capital, we concentrated specifically on natural capital associated with forest and peatland landscapes.

The remainder of this report is structured as follows:

- Overview of the scenario development process.
- Presentation of the scenarios.
- Overview of workshop activities.
- Initial results.
- Synthesis.
- Implications and next steps.

2. Scenario development process

The scenario development process was designed and conducted to meet aims associated with both of the two projects mentioned above. Specifically, the dual purposes of the scenarios were to: a) explore the future condition and values of natural capital, as well as the drivers of change that influence these; and b) act as contexts in which to assess stakeholders' perceptions of risks and opportunities facing natural capital, as well as responses to these. The second of these two aims is of most relevance to the Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital project, and is the main focus of this report. The first aim is more strongly associated with the project 'Bringing in participatory approaches to widen the scope of natural capital valuation', and outputs associated with this will be published at a later date.

With these aims in mind, it was desirable for the scenarios to explore a wide range of plausible future possibilities, and to structure different scenarios such that participants would have chance to identify a wide range of potential risks to natural capital. We therefore followed a 'morphological' scenario-building approach, which Johansen (2018) suggests is a pertinent approach for achieving these aims. Practically, this involved several activities, which were conducted, initially by participants in the first workshop, split into three 'breakout' groups, and then progressed by researchers from the James Hutton Institute. These are outlined, sequentially, below.

Timeline

To prompt participants to start thinking about plausible future developments, each group was tasked with creating a timeline, on which they were asked to plot events, trends, changes, policies, etc, that they perceived to have had a significant influence on forest-based and peatland-based natural capital in Scotland since 2010. They were then asked to extend the timeline up to 2045 (the Scottish Government’s target year for achieving Net Zero) and plot the events, trends, changes, policies, etc, they perceive as likely to influence natural capital in the future.

STEEP Analysis

We subsequently asked each group of participants to conduct a ‘STEEP analysis’ (see Duckett et al. (2022) for example) to identify ‘drivers of change’¹. This involved each group reviewing their timeline and identifying drivers of change associated with each of the social, technological, economic, environmental, and policy realms. Participants discussed the drivers they identified, as well as their potential impacts on natural capital, and then captured these on post-it notes, which they added to flipchart paper, under each of the STEEP categories.

Morphological Matrices

In the final session of the first workshop, we facilitated participants through the process of creating ‘morphological matrices’. These are matrices containing sets of plausible assumptions about how drivers of change could develop in the future (Johansen, 2018). Each group of participants was asked to select a driver from each of the STEEP categories, identified in the previous activity, and list them in the first column of the matrix. Each group then derived a set of assumptions, through deliberation, about how each driver could influence Scottish forest and peatland natural capital in the future, and note these assumptions in subsequent columns. Participants were asked to consider and include a mixture of positive, business as usual, and negative assumptions for each driver, as well as noting trade-offs and complementarities between different drivers. Unfortunately, there was only time for each group to explore assumptions about one driver from each of the STEEP categories.

Combining assumptions to create scenario narratives

The next steps were completed by James Hutton Institute researchers, following the first workshop. We typed-up the assumptions from all three groups’ morphological matrices, and then combined them into a single table, containing positive, business as

¹ ‘Drivers of change’ can be described as: “Factors that cause change in nature, anthropogenic assets, nature’s benefits to people and a good quality of life” Ferrier, S., Ninan, K., Leadley, P., Alkemade, R., Acosta-Michlik, L., Akçakaya, H. & Kabubo-Mariara, J. (2016). Summary for policymakers of the assessment report of the methodological assessment of scenarios and models of biodiversity and ecosystem services.

usual, and negative assumptions for each of the STEEP categories. The assumptions from across different groups were combined, where they contained similar themes, and then elaborated into narrative prose, describing plausible future conditions in 2045. These narratives were cross-checked by different members of the research team for plausibility and internal consistency (i.e. whether the assumptions made were logical and non-contradictory). We eventually developed three scenarios, one made up of positive assumptions, one of business as usual assumptions, and another of negative assumptions. It is important to note here, that what was considered positive, business as usual, and negative, for natural capital, was left open to participants in the first workshop. The value judgements made by participants are therefore, inevitably, reflected in the eventual scenarios. These should not be taken as definitive predictions of the future, nor should they be assumed to necessarily reflect the views of the researchers involved. Nonetheless, the scenarios provide a wide-ranging and interesting set of contexts in which to stimulate discussion about future risks, opportunities, and responses for natural capital.

Adding climate projections

Considering the focus of the Climate change impacts on natural capital project, we added to the qualitative narratives of assumptions, a set of climate projections showing projected changes in: 1) Mean Monthly Maximum Temperatures; 2) Mean Monthly Minimum Temperatures; 3) Mean Monthly Precipitation; and 4) Mean Monthly Climatic Water Balance, for Scotland, over the period 2020-2049, as compared with a historical baseline period of 1960-1989. The projections were presented as maps, produced by the James Hutton Institute as part of work supported by the Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division for the 'Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital' Project funded by the Scottish Government Strategic Research Programme 2022-2027. The data from which the projections were derived was provided by the UK Meteorological Office and UKCP18 Climate Projections. It is important to note that these projections are descriptions of possible future climate conditions, based on statistical models and projected trends. They are not predictions of what will happen, but assumptions based on available evidence. Further details on these projections can be found here: [The James Hutton Institute Climate Data Visualisation](#).

We added brief annotations, interpreting the projections for each climatic variable, to aid in participants' understanding, and also added reference to the projected conditions in the qualitative narratives. We randomly selected three projections from the ensemble available in the James Hutton Institute Climate Data Visualisation and allocated them to each of the three scenarios. The selected projections and the scenarios to which they were allocated were as follows:

- Scenario 1; Projection 15 (1.1C warmer; 9% wetter 2020-2049)
- Scenario 2; Projection 12 (3.8C warmer; 3% drier)

- Scenario 3; Projection 11 (2.6C warmer; 7% wetter)

The combined scenarios and climate projections were presented to participants prior to the second workshop, in order for them to have sufficient time to read-through and digest them, before using them to help explore risks, opportunities, and responses. The scenarios, as presented to participants, are presented as Annexes to this report. The next section explains the methodology used for exploring risks, opportunities and responses in the workshop.

3. Workshop activities

In the second of these two scenario planning workshops, and the one that is the focus of this report, we used the scenarios (see Annex 1) as contexts, in which to explore risks, opportunities and responses to them, together with participants. To help create conducive conditions for in-depth discussion and learning, we invited a maximum of 25-30 participants, around 20 of whom were able to attend on the day. The workshop was held online, using Microsoft Teams and the virtual collaboration platform, Miro. The online nature of the workshop meant it was less resource-intensive and enabled the participation of stakeholders from a range of different locations. Participants thought the discussions held were useful and interesting, though they also remarked that the interactions could have been enriched, and longer-term connections with others made, had the workshop been held in-person. The specific workshop activities were as follows.

Presentation of the scenarios

We initially shared the scenarios with participants, prior to the workshop, to give them chance to read through and digest the qualitative narratives and projections they would be working with in the workshop. We allocated each participant to one of three breakout groups, in advance, and then allocated each group one of the three scenarios to work with. Each participant therefore received the scenario allocated to their group to read beforehand.

At the start of the workshop, we presented summaries of all three scenarios to all of the participants, as well as an explanation of how they were developed, including the development of the climate projections. We emphasised that the scenarios were descriptions of plausible future conditions, based on informed assumptions, not definitive predictions of what will happen. We also stressed that the scenarios inherently reflected the views of participants in the first workshop and therefore were subjective. We instructed participants to use their group's scenario as a context in which to assess risks to natural capital, as well as response options and opportunities.

Identifying risks, opportunities, impacts and responses

Each of the three breakout groups was asked to discuss and identify and list risks and

opportunities for Scotland's natural capital, in their group's scenario, as well as potential responses to these. Participants were asked to populate a table in Miro with their responses, specifically including one column for the risks and opportunities they identified, another for the impacts, including any potential knock-on effects or 'chains of impact', that could occur as a result of each risk/opportunity, and another for responses that could help to mitigate or adapt to the risks posed to natural capital. In the final two columns, participants were asked to vote on whether they thought the likelihood, and then significance, of each risk or opportunity was high, medium or low.

Assessing wildfire risk and responses

As part of the workshop, we also explored wildfire as a specific example of a type of risk to natural capital in Scotland. We thus asked participants to imagine they were part of a taskforce, commissioned in March 2044, by the Scottish Government, to assess the risk of wildfire and identify potential responses to it in the following 12 months (2044-2045). We asked them to discuss the following questions and populate corresponding columns in a table in Miro with their responses:

- What is the likelihood of wildfire occurring in Scotland in the coming 12 months (2044-2045), in your group's scenario?
- Which areas of Scotland are likely to be most affected, in your scenario, and when?
- What impacts are wildfires likely to have for natural capital (including knock-on effects), in your scenario?
- What measures could be taken to mitigate/adapt to fire in your scenario?

At the end of the workshop, we had a brief plenary discussion with participants to review what they had discussed in their breakout groups. Initial summarised findings from the workshop discussions are presented in Section 5, below, whilst the tables that participants populated in Miro are presented in Annex 2.

4. Initial results

5.1 Types of risks and opportunities identified.

Scenario 1

The participants in Group 1 (working with Scenario 1) focused predominantly on socio-economic risks and opportunities posed to natural capital in Scotland. Displaying an awareness of complexity, participants often identified trade-offs and uncertainties associated with different risks and opportunities, without being prompted by facilitators. Participants suggested an opportunity, in that increased investment in natural capital, evident in Scenario 1, could lead to increased action on protecting and enhancing natural capital, for example by increasing possibilities for afforestation. Participants thought this could create positive feedback in which more natural capital would be created, with greater value, resulting in nature gaining equal importance, in

decision-making, to economic gross domestic product (GDP). However, the participants cautioned that forestry should not be prioritised at the expense of other aspects of landscape. Afforestation on organic soils was thought to risk creating increased net emissions, whilst greater tree cover was also perceived to increase fuel load for wildfires, as well as the risk of storm damage to trees.

Participants also suggested several risks. The first of which was highlighted as a potential weakness in the conditions described under this scenario (Scenario 1 – positive), in that the conditions described could result in weak legal mechanisms that are not brokered correctly. Natural capital schemes could therefore fail at the landscape scale, without long-term accountability.

Another perceived risk, associated with technology, was that human knowledge and skills for monitoring the state of natural capital could be eroded by artificial intelligence. However, participants also saw an opportunity here, in that human knowledge and skills could be redeployed to management of natural capital, whilst technology deals with continuous, real-time monitoring and mapping. Participants thought this could lead to increased capacity for trying and implementing different management options, with robust, continuous monitoring.

Another perceived socio-economic risk in Scenario 1 was a lack of funding for long-term projects, which could result in cash flow issues for natural capital. Relatedly, participants noted that in this scenario, Scotland could be considered a ‘bubble’ in that its good practices in managing natural capital may not be reflected elsewhere in the world. They thought this could result in a reduction in available funds for communities to continue their work, and thus disengagement by communities over time. Ultimately, participants thought this could result in natural capital going out of favour, resulting in a reversion to ‘business as usual’ and thus negating the benefits, in terms of greater ecosystem health and resilience in the face of climate adversity, assumed to have been achieved under Scenario 1.

Scenario 2

Based on the ‘business as usual’ scenario, Group 2 thought there was a high risk of water scarcity and drought, which could impact negatively on agriculture, as well as on Scotland’s ability to fight wildfires. However, they also saw an opportunity in that shifting patterns of precipitation could, conversely, improve agricultural productivity in some areas. Participants also foresaw a high risk of flooding, which could result in loss of natural capital, as well as damage to infrastructure and communities. The risk was felt to be severe due to the likelihood of consecutive or simultaneous flood events which would multiply impacts. These participants also thought that the reduction in management of natural capital, outlined in this scenario, would likely produce a high to medium risk of build-up of brushwood, which would act as fuel load for wildfires. This,

coupled with prolonged periods of warm, dry weather and a reduction in management of fire breaks may provide opportunities for wildfires to spread, causing biodiversity loss, CO₂ emissions, and damage to fragile peatland areas.

From a socio-economic perspective, participants noted that with increases in hybrid working highlighted in the scenario, as well as rapid urbanisation, the group suggested that inherited, generational, local knowledge on working with natural capital and managing the land for resilience would be being lost. Participants thought that the reduction in management of natural capital, noted in the scenario, indicates a broader reduction in social capital in terms of skills, resources, capacity, and capability, and disconnected knowledge, regarding management of natural capital and wildfires. The participants thought this could lead to increased system fragility.

Participants also thought the increased warm, dry weather in Scenario 2 could provide opportunities for increased recreational activities, which would draw urban dwellers to the countryside, potentially increasing local income and gross value-added. This may provide an opportunity for increasing engagement activities to address current gaps in understanding between rural and urban populations. However, it was noted that this may also lead to more accidental wildfires, necessitating a field reversal of the access code to ban recreational fires except in particular circumstances (e.g. planned muirburn).

Scenario 3

Group 3 (working with Scenario 3) concentrated more on biophysical risks. A particularly pertinent risk they identified was that of reduced genetic diversity in commercial and conservation forestry species, which participants thought would reduce the resilience of trees to pests and diseases. They thought this could also lead to increased requirements for widespread felling, reduction of the economic value of forest products, as well as other impacts affecting regulating ecosystem services, such as soil stability. Participants thought this risk was particularly acute in this scenario because of the creation of poorly planned plantations of a single, fast-growing, fire-resistant species (e.g. eucalyptus) in efforts to rapidly bolster capacity for carbon sequestration. Participants thought this could also lead to more widespread homogenisation of flora, reduction of suitable habitats for wildlife, and subsequent impacts on landscape character, creating a vicious cycle of vulnerability to climate hazards, including the vulnerability of people and properties to wildfire.

Participants in Group 3 also considered the effects of wildfires and muirburn, when beyond what is prescribed as necessary for creating conditions for wildlife gaming. Participants thought this could result in loss of habitats and biodiversity, leading to a shift from forest and shrubland to grassland ecosystems, loss of carbon, water pollution, and increased water temperature in rivers, with negative consequences for

the survival of salmonid species. Participants also foresaw similar impacts associated with the degradation of peatlands, such as peat erosion, soil runoff, water pollution, and downstream flooding. Participants thought these ecological changes could be accompanied by an increase in the public cost of suppressing fire from land and air, and risks of injury and death for those working to control fire. They also mentioned that current positive trends of restoration of peatlands and forests, as well as associated income-generation through carbon credits, could be undermined by a higher prevalence of fire.

Participants also discussed risks posed to water resources, as a result of increased extractive management and prolonged dry periods. As a consequence, they thought habitats could be degraded, salinity intrusion and deoxygenation could increase, and thus biodiversity and genetic diversity could be lost. Participants expected this would impact upon important economic species (e.g. salmon), and also increase the costs of supplying water for society. Mention was also made of the likely decline in cultural ecosystem services associated with water.

Group 3 did also consider socio-economic risks in their scenario. One such risk they considered was the potential for restrictions on public access to upland areas, as a result of increased occurrence of wildfire. The participants thought this may have negative effects on recreational activities and tourism, which could also lead to a decline in other cultural values associated with mental and physical health. Additional social risks that participants identified were associated with the destiny of rural communities. On one hand, drier conditions could result in an influx of people to rural areas for living and recreational purposes, consolidating and strengthening rural communities of place, though participants recognised the need to ensure housing development to meet increased demand does not make housing, and other living costs, unaffordable for local people. On the other hand, greater environmental risks could result in further reduction of job opportunities in rural areas, declining rural populations, and even abandonment of certain areas, resulting in loss of local knowledge and diminished responses to environmental risks.

5.2 Types of responses that people suggested.

Scenario 1

In terms of responses to the risks and opportunities identified, participants in Group 1 thought diversification and integration were important, economically, biophysically and politically. Participants suggested there is a need for natural capital markets to consider multiple benefits and risks, and also for valuation to consider natural capital functions, as opposed to just features. They thought this may be supported by the establishment of ecosystem markets that go beyond a focus on carbon sequestration, and that ensure fair payments for rural organisations and capacity-building for resilience work. Participants perceived that this could lead to greater support for different management

options, including multi-objective forestry, which would encourage diversification (e.g. of tree species), and thus improve resilience. Diversification and management for multiple objectives, in particular, were considered high-likelihood and high-significance opportunities. However, the importance of continuous, long-term monitoring of the benefits of natural capital was raised as important to the success of natural capital schemes, and participants suggested this should be integrally designed into such schemes from their outset.

In terms of integration, participants thought there was a need for integrated long-term economic development, integrated fire management plans, and overall better governance of natural capital management. Participants thought there was a need for integration and engagement of different communities, including businesses, to help them stay connected to the landscape and able to benefit from schemes, as well as global engagement and partnerships. One suggestion was that this could be supported through more participatory models for multi-year funding schemes. Global knowledge exchange and maintenance of global governance frameworks were also considered essential for maintaining progress on positive management of nature and tackling the challenges of climate change.

Scenario 2

Participants in Group 2 thought drought and water scarcity could potentially be managed by capturing water in times of plenty, planting vegetation to retain water, and tapping into local knowledge on the best plant choices for resilience. This could be addressed through changing vegetation to retain water upstream, planning flood mitigation to balance the use of hard engineering and natural flood management, and investing in solutions which prevent flooding in the first place, rather than paying to fix damages caused. Participants thought that increased fuel load for fire could be managed through the creation of firebreaks, scheduled muirburns, land use change to prevent increases in fuel load, a push towards local ownership and management rather than large scale investment, and the upgrading of firefighting tools (i.e. helicopters). They also suggested that consideration of different approaches to peatland restoration processes, which are currently not delivering as planned, may offer good opportunities for climate change mitigation through carbon sequestration.

These participants thought that the loss of local knowledge regarding natural capital management could be countered by increased community ownership and place-based education, which they perceived as leading to greater literacy of place, more resilient landscapes and the development of holistic, locally appropriate solutions. Newcomers to rural communities could be encouraged to join local initiatives and integrate with local communities, which could create an opportunity for moving away from the rural/urban dichotomy and increasing understanding and support for land management measures. Under this scenario, participants highlighted the importance

of ensuring that housing, services and resources for rural populations, and particularly those who actively manage land and natural capital and may be paid less well than hybrid workers, are maintained.

Scenario 3

In terms of responses to rebalance the impacts identified in Scenario 3, participants suggested it would be important to introduce tree species that are able to control pests, maintain species diversity during restocking, and gene conservation units that allow adaptation to climate change and other threats. Participants thought it would be pertinent to educate timber customers on the risks of single species plantations and to increase the acceptance of alternative wooded products arising from different forestry species. In terms of reducing habitat degradation, participants thought better planning and management could focus on peatland soil conservation, including rewetting dried peat soils, and removing perverse incentives that drive exploitative activities. Participants suggested strategies such as the use of drip irrigation, changing to drought-tolerant crop varieties, establishing water conservation plans, and reusing treated wastewater. A greater use of ponds and designed wetlands to keep water on the land was also suggested.

As regards the responses to fire, participants highlighted the importance of considering fire risk in planting guidance for forests, for example by excluding the species that are more sensitive to fire and introducing broad-leaved species to form fire shelter belts. They also thought it would be important to guarantee easy access points for responding to wildfires, as well as using innovative technology to monitor and extinguish them. Participants also suggested targeting peatland restoration, through rewetting, could help to create natural fire breaks. Additionally, participants thought land could be managed in ways that would make peatlands less prone to fires, such as by restricting muirburn for game sport shooting, in favour of other more sustainable income-generation activities on estates. Participants considered information-sharing and collaboration between communities and stakeholders as important for organising social responses and enhancing social capital to spread more sustainable forms of land management. Participants thought planning restrictions and increasing educational campaigns to inform people on how to behave to reduce fire ignition and propagation were pertinent.

5.3 Wildfire as an example of risk

Scenario 1

Participants in Group 1 considered the likelihood of wildfire in Scotland to be high, overall, in 2044. One participant interjected from the outset that Scotland already experiences a high occurrence of wildfire, which may have influenced the responses of others. There were, though, an interesting range of responses regarding spatial and

temporal variations in future wildfire occurrence, perhaps indicative of the variability illustrated in the projections. One participant emphasised, on the basis of prior knowledge, that the likelihood of wildfire is greatest in spring, but severity is likely to be higher in late summer. There was recognition that, in this scenario, fuel load is likely to be higher across the board, and that there would be variable ‘spates’ of wildfire conditions. There was also a perception, based on the climate projections, that the east of Scotland would be drier in 2044-45, so could be more vulnerable, but that sporadic, intense droughts in west could contribute to short-term periods of high fire risk.

Participants considered the potential impacts of wildfires to be severe. They thought that higher continuous fuel loads, and more fires, burning for longer, and with higher intensity at certain times could cause landscape-scale damage or destruction of natural capital assets. Whilst they acknowledged the large-scale destruction of natural capital could increase the value of what remains, participants also thought damage caused to peat and the roots of trees, including through fires smouldering at a low level, could result in destruction of carbon stores. In terms of socio-economic impacts, participants thought that fire services could become over-stretched and collapse, and there could increasingly be impacts on the fringes of urban areas.

In terms of responses to wildfire, participants thought there was a need for integrated, strategic management of wildfire to be built-into natural capital approaches. They perceived that this would require education to raise awareness of risks and fire dynamics. Participants also perceived a need for real-time observations of wildfire conditions, and for those responsible for management to follow best practice, based on empirical evidence (e.g. fire breaks). Relatedly, participants emphasised a need for appropriate investment in the groups responsible for fire management.

Scenario 2

Based on the ‘business as usual’ scenario, Group 2 thought there was a medium to high risk of wildfire in Scotland in the year 2044-2045. Areas most likely to be affected, according to the group, ranged from ‘everywhere’ to rural areas, upland areas where muirburn is prevalent, degraded peatlands, and forest sites where recreational use is high. The greatest risk was considered to be in summer. The impacts of wildfire under this scenario, according to the group, included risks to life and property, ecological damage, and huge releases of greenhouse gases from burning peatlands. It was thought that the landscape would change, causing communities to feel excluded, and prohibitions would increase in response to wildfire incidents.

Possible responses that participants raised included the introduction of firebreaks and controlled burns to reduce risk, changes in the Access Code and Muirburn Code to ban recreational fires, raising public awareness and educational content on how to prevent wildfires, and increasing community land ownership and management.

Participants suggested that grazing animals on heather moorland may help to reduce fuel load, although it was noted that livestock can damage fragile peatlands unless well managed. The development of a national high-level strategy which incorporates grassroots learning from local communities into top-down policy was thought to be important. Technical solutions were also considered, and there was some discussion about artificial rainfall and whether this was a cost-effective method of extinguishing wildfires. It was felt that the resources to protect the whole of Scotland from wildfire may not be available and as such, some level of prioritisation may be necessary and sacrificial areas may need to be delineated. It was also highlighted that dealing with increased risk of flooding by planting trees and increasing vegetation may actually increase fuel load and cause more wildfires. A mechanism to determine the most appropriate solution in each set of circumstances that minimises trade-offs would be helpful.

Scenario 3

Participants in Group 3 considered the overall risk of wildfire to be high, especially across the East and Central Highlands. They considered the East coast to have the highest average temperatures, but highlighted that the West and North are characterised by the most vulnerable habitats, as their flora is less drought tolerant and more likely to produce fuel load. Peak fire season was considered quite prolonged from early spring to mid-late summer, because of the increase in dry and warm summer conditions.

Participants speculated that there could be social implications of increased wildfire, in terms of human migration and displacement from areas of high risk, disruption to the movement of goods and impacts to local economies and communities. In addition, significant economic impacts on agricultural activities, timber production and other related activities such as the whisky industry were mentioned. Participants also thought that if the landscape continues to change, irreversibly, from forest to grassland and heather after fire, there could be impacts on cultural services, such as the loss of connection with the countryside. Conversely, some positive consequences were also suggested, in that increased fire could enable more nutrient cycling and habitat renewal, which could help maintain more open habitats, and thus reduce fuel load.

In terms of responses, participants thought there was a need for new regulation, improved planning and land use management, and education. For example, they thought there was a need for stricter regulation of recreational activities that may induce accidental fires, such as barbequing, whilst land use management practices should include consideration for fire risk by incorporating fire breaks and rewetting peatlands and wetlands, as well as limiting the impacts of fire at urban peripheries by reducing fuel load around settlements. Participants also thought planning should include generation of local response plans, and well-planned access route to areas at

high risks, to guarantee firefighting intervention. They identified a need for initiatives to be coordinated by improving human and social capital through education of local residents and visitors on the risk of wildfires, as well as information campaigns and training on the correct behaviour to adopt in case of fire. However, participants recognised these initiatives could only be successful, if well-coordinated and sufficiently funded. The group therefore suggested that blended funding approaches for fire control, response and prevention would be beneficial, for example by drawing on private funding for prevention and state funding for fire suppression. They also thought that remote sensing could help provide continuous monitoring of potential fire risks in the landscape, which may help to facilitate early warning systems and quick responses to fires. Generally, participants thought there was a need to shift or adapt rural economies and associated land uses to minimise the risk and potential impacts of fire, such as transitioning from agriculture to rewetted areas, or to game-related tourism in drier areas.

5. Synthesis

Interestingly, there was considerable variation in the types of risks and opportunities that participants in different groups identified, suggesting that the approach of using different scenarios to help explore a range of risks was successful. Although, given the roles and expertise of the participants in this workshop, it is likely they would have brought up many of the risks identified anyway. Indeed, some participants reflected that they felt the scenarios had in fact limited what they were able to discuss, though it is likely the limited time available for the workshop also played a role in this.

In terms of risks, the types of risks that participants identified included climatic extremes, resulting in water scarcity as well as floods in different conditions, as well as increased potential for more frequent and severe wildfires. Habitat loss and degradation, including loss of genetic diversity, were expected to compound these climatic issues, potentially leading to large-scale damage and loss of natural capital and degradation of the values associated with them. Participants also considered the effects of such risks for the people whose lives and livelihoods are inextricably linked to natural capital in Scotland, fearing that such large-scale degradation and damage would have a detrimental effect on rural communities, potentially leading to increased population decline and loss of invaluable local knowledge.

In terms of opportunities, increased investment in nature, through natural capital approaches was considered potentially beneficial, though the importance of integrating multiple objectives (i.e. not just planting fast-growing trees for carbon credits), management options and different funding sources was considered essential. Technological development was also considered an opportunity, particularly for monitoring the condition of natural capital and the effects of natural capital approaches, as well as for monitoring and responding to wildfire. Importantly, whilst the potential for

local communities and their knowledge to decline was acknowledged, participants also recognised that the connectedness of rural communities, and the wealth of intergenerational knowledge associated with this, represents an opportunity for improving the management of Scotland's natural capital.

Turning to response options, the discussions across all three scenarios highlight the importance of diversification, as well as integrated, strategic planning, to address the risks and take advantage of opportunities identified. There was a clear emphasis on the importance of diversifying the types of natural capital included in natural capital schemes, as well as the types of markets associated with them, and the types of funding sources that support them. Genetic diversity was also considered essential for the resilience of natural capital. In terms of monitoring, there was a suggestion that the overall condition of ecosystems should be monitored, rather than just valuing the individual natural capital 'assets' therein.

Integration, in a broad sense, can be considered essential. The workshop discussions suggest that governance of natural capital should include strong and coherent legal frameworks to support regulation at different levels. These ought to take into account different management options in different parts of the landscape, at different times, in a holistic way (e.g. water retention, different tree species, well-planned muirburn, and peat restoration). Achieving this was considered to require engagement and knowledge exchange at the local, national, and global scales, as well as different funding sources. Empowerment of local communities was also considered important, including through community ownership, and drawing on their knowledge to support the resilience of natural capital.

In terms of wildfire, specifically, the perceived risk is high, as a result of increased fuel load and conducive climatic conditions in the future. There was also good recognition, among this group of participants at least, of the spatial and temporal variability of potential future fire conditions. The perceived severity is also high, with participants recognising the potential for substantial damage to natural capital, and associated release of carbon, with detrimental effects for the value of natural capital. From a socio-economic perspective there is also the potential for damage to human lives and livelihoods, including disruption of agricultural production, and displacement of people. Responses to wildfire risk need to be integrated, including diverse management options, strategic planning, and monitoring being incorporated into natural capital schemes from the outset. To be successful, such responses will require education and increased awareness of wildfire, as well as robust and coherent regulation.

6. Implications and Next steps

The findings from this workshop indicate the importance of the following:

- Considering a holistic range of risks, opportunities, and associated responses is essential. The use of different scenarios can be useful for facilitating such an assessment, but would be enriched by more time, and in-person interactions.
- Diversification, in terms of genetic diversity in nature, as well as in terms of what is included in natural capital markets, and the funding used to support natural capital schemes, can help to bolster resilience to the risks and take advantage of opportunities for natural capital.
- Taking an integrated approach to managing natural capital, including integration of appropriate options for managing different aspects of the landscape, engagement and knowledge exchange across scales, monitoring, and well-planned, coherent policy and legal frameworks, is critical to the success of responses to risks and opportunities.
- The knowledge, experience, and connectedness of rural communities to the landscape are vital resources for supporting the resilience of natural capital, but are themselves threatened by the risks identified herein. Engagement and empowerment of local communities may therefore be invaluable in ensuring the resilience of natural capital to present and future risks.

The next steps in this research will involve:

- Further elaboration of findings from the workshop to inform development of tools, such as risk maps, and contribute to development of a 'risk and opportunities assessment framework', for supporting decision-making about risks to natural capital.
- Systematic assessment of the effects the identified risks could have for the values associated with natural capital in Scotland.
- We also intend to write an academic paper discussing the findings of this workshop.

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Annexes 1 – Scenarios used for exploring risks, opportunities and responses

3.1 Scenario 1

Qualitative narrative (based on ‘positive’ assumptions about Social, Technology, Economic, Environmental, and Policy drivers, from Workshop 1).

Under this scenario, rural populations are empowered through strong local governance, local democracy and local participation. Policies associated with Community Wealth Building, and the Good Food Nation Bill, promote local procurement and enable a circular economy. This, together with strong community ownership and partnership-based ownership of natural assets, ensures that local resources are used for the benefit of local wealth and wellbeing.

The post-COVID-19 trend of hybrid working continues to grow, which is encouraging increased immigration to stronger and more resilient rural communities. This promotes innovation and economic activity, yet an aging rural population ensures wisdom, collaboration and shared skills are valued, which ensures the housing, services and infrastructure needed for growing rural populations are developed sensitively and in harmony with local landscapes.

Taken together, these drivers enable rural communities to take stronger ownership of natural capital and its management. The rootedness of rural communities in the landscape, and their nuanced understanding of it, contributes to positive management that is based on care, rather than unsustainable exploitation. Land is managed for multiple uses, including polycultural, regenerative agriculture, and well-managed conservation and rewilding, which strengthens the ability of natural capital to provide regulating services. Community-led tourism fosters a greater awareness of the natural capital that underpins and is affected by tourism, as well as a sensitivity to the diverse types of values associated with the landscape. This leads to greater demand among tourists to experience a varied and biodiverse landscape, and a less-exploitative model of tourism.

Increased efforts to combat climate change help attract more investment in private and integrated carbon markets. Nature finance develops rapidly via investment from multiple sources, including private finance and new income streams. This means more money is available for natural capital management and increased public-private finance. However, the strength of local governance and community ownership ensures that private investment in natural capital is conducted in a responsible manner, that recognises a responsibility to preserve and enhance a more holistic range of values (including community values associated with place, and intrinsic values, on an equal level with economic and utilitarian values). It also encourages transition to more sustainable business models and works for the benefit of local communities.

Meanwhile, technological developments, including the role of cheap and accessible artificial intelligence, lead to improvements in the accuracy of biodiversity data, for example through LiDAR and e-DNA. This enables better monitoring of the condition of natural capital assets, as well as the risks posed to them. There is better understanding of the impacts of climate change, as well as of changes to the ecological balance, and how resilience may be supported, meaning that resource-planning and decision-making are more informed. A more joined-up and holistic approach to meeting Net Zero targets strengthens synergies across policies and sectors, and fosters longer-term political decision-making. Land management targets and incentives (including those related to carbon sequestration) are tailored to be appropriate for specific contexts, which improves their chance of being met, whilst Net Zero sets a positive trajectory for meeting future targets. The health of social-ecological systems and their resilience to extreme weather events starts to improve and there is optimism that many of the effects of climate change can be managed and mitigated. However, whilst the above trends make Scotland a world-leader in mitigation and adaptation to the climate and biodiversity crises, the global community is slow to follow suit. This means global greenhouse gas emissions have remained high, and as the below climate projections show, the impacts of climate change are being starkly felt.

**NB The assumptions expressed above are derived from the knowledge and opinions of workshop participants. They do not necessarily represent the views of the James Hutton Institute.*

Climate projection

The following section presents projected changes in: 1) Mean Monthly Maximum Temperatures; 2) Mean Monthly Minimum Temperatures; 3) Mean Monthly Precipitation; and 4) Mean Monthly Climatic Water Balance over the period 2020-2049, as compared with a historical baseline period of 1960-1989. The projections are presented as maps, below, which have been produced by the James Hutton Institute as part of work supported by the Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division for the 'Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital' Project funded by the Scottish Government Strategic Research Programme 2022-2027. The data from which the projections are derived is provided by the UK Meteorological Office and UKCP18 Climate Projections. It is important to note that these projections are descriptions of possible future climate conditions, based on statistical models and projected trends. They are not predictions of what will happen, but assumptions based on available evidence. Further details on these projections can be found here: [The James Hutton Institute Climate Data Visualisation](#).

The projections included in this scenario are taken from the James Hutton Institute Climate Data Visualisation Ensemble Member 15, *in which the climate of Scotland is projected to be **1.1C warmer and 9% wetter*** in the period 2020-2049.

Figure 1 – Changes in Mean Monthly Maximum Temperature

Changes in mean monthly maximum temperature over the period 2020-2049 as compared to the historical baseline period 1960-1989 for the ensemble member 15

The maps show that *mean monthly maximum temperature* (average of daily maximum temperatures across each month) increases in most areas, and in most months, for the period 2020-2049. The increase is strongest in late-spring and summer, especially in the months of May, July, August and September, and is more acute in Eastern and Southern areas. In a few locations, monthly mean maximum temperatures are projected to decrease slightly or stay the same, particularly Northwestern areas, in December.

Figure 2 - Changes in Mean Monthly Minimum Temperature

Changes in mean monthly minimum temperature over the period 2020-2049 as compared to the historical baseline period 1960-1989 for the ensemble member 15

The maps show that *mean monthly minimum temperature* (average of daily minimum temperatures across each month) increases in most areas, and in most months, for the period 2020-2049. The increase is strongest in the summer months, especially the months of July, August and September. The exception is December, in which the minimum temperature remains similar in most places, and is even cooler in some areas.

Figure 3 – Changes in Mean Monthly Precipitation

Changes in mean monthly precipitation over the period 2020-2049 as compared to the historical baseline period 1960-1989 for the ensemble member 15

The maps show considerable variation in the percentage of precipitation change (extent to which the mean of total monthly precipitation is projected to increase or decrease), both according to location and time of year. In February and April, substantial areas of Scotland are receiving higher mean precipitation than in 1960-1989, whilst in August and September, that is reversed, with much of Scotland receiving lower precipitation. In other months, there are differences between Eastern and Southern areas, which receive higher precipitation, and Western and Northern areas, which receive similar or lower precipitation.

Figure 4 – Changes in Mean Monthly Climatic Water Balance

Changes in mean monthly climatic water balance over the period 2020-2049 as compared to the historical baseline period 1960-1989 for the ensemble member 15

The maps show considerable variation in the *climatic water balance* (amount of water received through precipitation (mm), minus amount of water lost to the atmosphere through evapotranspiration), both according to location and time of year. In February, much of Scotland is wetter, especially in western areas, whilst in May, August and September, much of Scotland is considerably drier, again especially in the west. Throughout the year, there is notable variation between locations, with some areas becoming wetter (often eastern and southern areas), and others becoming drier (often northwestern areas). This is particularly observable in October – January.

3.2 Scenario 2

Qualitative narrative (based on ‘business as usual’ assumptions about Social, Technology, Economic, Environmental, and Policy drivers, from Workshop 1).

Technology is supporting the continued growth of hybrid working, which enables people to live and work in rural areas. This reduces transport emissions from commuters, and for some, living and working in a rural community encourages stronger connections with local nature, because they are constantly encountering the local landscape, and therefore more strongly rooted in it. Additionally, growing numbers of people have multiple jobs and roles, which supports a more pluralistic economy, while there is also growing support for local products and services.

However, on balance, local business continues to decline in rural areas, and there remains limited capacity for ‘green’ jobs in rural areas. Additionally, hybrid working enables people to work from anywhere in the world, resulting in more ‘digital nomads’ who move frequently between different places. As such, there is still net outward migration of people from rural communities, especially young people. The aging population means funding for rural communities is primarily used for healthcare to support the aging population, whilst for some people, working from home means working longer hours, which results in them becoming more isolated, and in fact losing connection with their local area. This declining rural population is resulting in a loss of skills and knowledge for managing local natural capital, as well as reduced demand for the services it provides, locally.

Policies such as Community Wealth Building and Good Food Nation exist, but their strength and impact remain variable and uncertain. Rural communities have limited power to enact change and preserve biodiversity. In contrast, high-income second homeowners wield significant power over how natural capital is managed. Tourism continues to be exploitative, providing only seasonal employment for rural populations and degrading natural capital. Peat restoration is occurring, but continues to be slow, whilst large swathes of land continue to be managed for high-impact and unsustainable land uses, such as hunting, for the wealthy, whilst rewilding has yet to be properly defined and understood. Housing, businesses and infrastructure are often developed insensitively, for example on floodplains, or without due consideration for local communities and existing infrastructure.

Climate change issues are receiving greater attention, leading to increased action locally and nationally, whilst COP enables global collaborative action. Action against climate change is being taken, but progress is slow, and meeting Net Zero targets is a struggle and faces many challenges. Lobbying by proponents of extractive and high-emissions industries remains strong, and hybrid working generates greater usage of

cloud servers, which results in higher emissions from supercomputers. Although nature finance is exploring the potential for blended finance and new markets, as well as developing codes and standards of practice, it remains predominantly unregulated and voluntary, focusing primarily on uncertain and unstable carbon markets.

As can be seen in the climate projections, the Scottish climate has become considerably hotter and drier. This places growing stress on natural capital, exacerbated by more frequent and intense climatic extremes. Trends of habitat destruction and ecological change continue, whilst pests and pandemics proliferate. These changes require rapid learning about the ecological impacts of climate change, which helps manage them to some extent, though there remain significant ‘known unknowns’ (e.g. we know certain types of pests will proliferate, but we don’t know when) and ‘unknown unknowns’ (unanticipated challenges that will arise). Data about natural capital condition remains poor-quality, sub-national coverage and not universally accessible, which makes accurately understanding and measuring the impacts of these changes a challenge.

**NB The assumptions expressed above are derived from the knowledge and opinions of workshop participants. They do not necessarily represent the views of the James Hutton Institute.*

Climate projection

The following section presents projected changes in: 1) Mean Monthly Maximum Temperatures; 2) Mean Monthly Minimum Temperatures; 3) Mean Monthly Precipitation; and 4) Mean Monthly Climatic Water Balance over the period 2020-2049, as compared with a historical baseline period of 1960-1989. The projections are presented as maps, below, which have been produced by the James Hutton Institute as part of work supported by the Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division for the JHI-D5-2 ‘Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital’ Project funded by the Scottish Government Strategic Research Programme 2022-2027. The data from which the projections are derived is provided by the UK Meteorological Office and UKCP18 Climate Projections. It is important to note that these projections are descriptions of possible future climate conditions, based on statistical models and projected trends. They are not predictions of what will happen, but assumptions based on available evidence. Further details on these projections can be found here: [The James Hutton Institute Climate Data Visualisation](#).

The projections included in this scenario are taken from the James Hutton Institute Climate Data Visualisation Ensemble Member 12, *in which the climate of Scotland is projected to be **3.8C warmer and 3% drier*** in the period 2020-2049.

Figure 5 – Changes in Mean Monthly Maximum Temperature

Changes in mean monthly maximum temperature over the period 2020-2049 as compared to the historical baseline period 1960-1989 for the ensemble member 12

The maps show that *mean monthly maximum temperature* (average of daily maximum temperatures across each month) increases across almost all of Scotland, in all months, for the period 2020-2049. The increase is strongest in late-spring and late-summer, although considerable maximum temperature increases also occur in February and November. It is notable that central northern areas, including the Cairngorms National Park, experience much higher maximum temperatures in April and May, compared with the 1960-1989 baseline.

Figure 6 – Changes in Mean Monthly Minimum Temperature

Changes in mean monthly minimum temperature over the period 2020-2049 as compared to the historical baseline period 1960-1989 for the ensemble member 12

The maps show that *mean monthly minimum temperature* (average of daily minimum temperatures across each month) increases in most areas, and in most months, for the period 2020-2049. The increase is strong throughout the year. The increase in minimum temperatures is particularly stark in February, reaching as much as 8C higher in many areas. Central northern areas, including the Cairngorms National Park, particularly experience higher minimum temperatures in November, December, and February through to May.

Figure 7 - Changes in Mean Monthly Precipitation

Changes in mean monthly precipitation over the period 2020-2049 as compared to the historical baseline period 1960-1989 for the ensemble member 12

The maps show considerable variation in the percentage of *precipitation* change (extent to which the mean of total monthly precipitation is projected to increase or decrease), both according to location and time of year. In February and April, substantial areas of Scotland are receiving higher mean precipitation than in 1960-1989, whilst in May - October, that is reversed, with much of Scotland receiving lower precipitation, especially in late-summer. In some months, there are differences between Eastern and Southern areas, which receive higher precipitation, and Western and Northern areas, which receive similar or lower precipitation.

Figure 8 - Changes in Mean Monthly Climatic Water Balance

Changes in mean monthly climatic water balance over the period 2020-2049 as compared to the historical baseline period 1960-1989 for the ensemble member 12

The maps show a decrease in the *climatic water balance* (amount of water received through precipitation (mm), minus amount of water lost to the atmosphere through evapotranspiration), for much of Scotland, in most months. In February, much of Scotland is wetter, but from May – October, most of the country is drier. This is especially the case in western areas from September through to January, though some eastern and southern areas are actually slightly wetter in November to January.

3.3 Scenario 3

Qualitative narrative (based on ‘negative’ assumptions about Social, Technology, Economic, Environmental, and Policy drivers, from Workshop 1).

An intensive and extractive, capitalist economic model prevails, emphasising intensive farming, monocultures, exploitative tourism, and extensive land use for energy production. Policies aimed at Community Wealth Building and Good Food Nation have largely failed, and the power of large, corporate, external actors, such as supermarkets, is further consolidated and strengthened. Economic benefits from the exploitation of natural capital move outside rural communities to external actors. Unregulated nature finance creates unequal distribution of benefits. Targets are not made for the public good, while opportunities for corporations to invest in natural capital to offset their emissions act as a disincentive for reducing emissions and changing to more sustainable business models.

Meanwhile, a continued shift towards home and hybrid working creates increasing demand for housing in rural areas, but this is met without sufficient consideration for sustainability, service provision, or cultural sensitivities for local communities. Wealthy homeowners drive-up house prices, displacing local people from rural communities. This results in a loss of local resilience, through degradation of cultural and community values associated with place and community cohesion, as well as causing pollution and degradation of the natural environment, including increased risk of wildfires.

Increasing climatic extremes, combined with a degraded natural environment are compounded by slow and unambitious actions towards meeting Net Zero. Targets continue to focus on carbon, at the expense of biodiversity, and are increasingly ignored, or dropped entirely. Protectionist and politically isolationist policies, in relation to climate change, prevail. This means that actions to mitigate and manage the impacts of climate change on natural capital are failing, and its effects are becoming increasingly obvious. Ecosystem collapse, loss of ecosystem services, and large-scale biodiversity loss increasingly seem inevitable.

Despite this, our ability to monitor and understand these impacts is hindered by poor-quality data. There is a reduction of data integration, data holders are not collaborative and do not share their insights, and there is a lack of regional specificity in data and insights from it. Additionally, fewer people living in rural areas means many impacts, such as unseen wildfires, go unnoticed. This poor-quality data, together with machine bias in artificial intelligence, creates a high risk of poor decision-making, as well as misuse and misunderstanding of data, resulting in increased uncertainty and confused messaging.

This has a knock-on effect that public trust in, and accountability of, data and data users, are undermined. Additionally, failure to meet targets means that public trust in

political integrity is undermined. Attempts to improve public relations, in this regard, incentivise greenwashing and simplistic, poorly-planned actions, such as unplanned and uninformed rewilding and afforestation that result in reduced access to the landscape, increased conflicts, acceptance of invasive species, and putting the wrong trees in the wrong places, resulting in unintended consequences. Society largely gives up on action against climate change, allowing nature to be neglected and the effects of climate change to go unabated. This is especially concerning, given that the below climate projections show considerable changes in temperature and precipitation, as well as increasing climatic variability.

**NB The assumptions expressed above are derived from the knowledge and opinions of workshop participants. They do not necessarily represent the views of the James Hutton Institute.*

Climate projection

The following section presents projected changes in: 1) Mean Monthly Maximum Temperatures; 2) Mean Monthly Minimum Temperatures; 3) Mean Monthly Precipitation; and 4) Mean Monthly Climatic Water Balance over the period 2020-2049, as compared with a historical baseline period of 1960-1989. The projections are presented as maps, below, which have been produced by the James Hutton Institute as part of work supported by the Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division for the JHI-D5-2 'Climate Change Impacts on Natural Capital' Project funded by the Scottish Government Strategic Research Programme 2022-2027. The data from which the projections are derived is provided by the UK Meteorological Office and UKCP18 Climate Projections. It is important to note that these projections are descriptions of possible future climate conditions, based on statistical models and projected trends. They are not predictions of what will happen, but assumptions based on available evidence. Further details on these projections can be found here: [The James Hutton Institute Climate Data Visualisation](#).

The projections included in this scenario are taken from the James Hutton Institute Climate Data Visualisation Ensemble Member 11, *in which the climate of Scotland is projected to be **2.6C warmer and 7% wetter** in the period 2020-2049.*

Figure 9 - Changes in Mean Monthly Maximum Temperature

Changes in mean monthly maximum temperature over the period 2020-2049 as compared to the historical baseline period 1960-1989 for the ensemble member 11

The maps show that *mean monthly maximum temperature* (average of daily maximum temperatures across each month) increases across almost all of Scotland, in all months, for the period 2020-2049. The increase is high in January – May, and July – September, and slightly lower in June and October – December. The increase is highest, for most areas, in May.

Figure 10 - Changes in Mean Monthly Minimum Temperature

Changes in mean monthly minimum temperature over the period 2020-2049 as compared to the historical baseline period 1960-1989 for the ensemble member 11

The maps show that *mean monthly minimum temperature* (average of daily minimum temperatures across each month) increases across almost all of Scotland, throughout the year, for the period 2020-2049. The increase in minimum temperatures is strongest in January – March, and is particularly acute in northwestern and north-central areas, including Highland areas, reaching as much as 8C higher in many areas.

Figure 11 - Changes in Mean Monthly Precipitation

Changes in mean monthly precipitation over the period 2020-2049 as compared to the historical baseline period 1960-1989 for the ensemble member 11

The maps show variation in the percentage of *precipitation change* (extent to which the mean of total monthly precipitation is projected to increase or decrease), both according to location and time of year. In February and July, substantial areas of Scotland are receiving higher mean precipitation than in 1960-1989, whilst in August - October, that is reversed, with much of Scotland receiving lower precipitation, especially in September. In several months, there are differences between Eastern and Southern areas, which receive higher precipitation, and Western and Northern areas, which receive similar or lower precipitation, although this is reversed in January and February.

Figure 12 - Changes in Mean monthly Climatic Water Balance

Changes in mean monthly climatic water balance over the period 2020-2049 as compared to the historical baseline period 1960-1989 for the ensemble member 11

The maps show considerable variation in the *climatic water balance* (amount of water received through precipitation (mm), minus amount of water lost to the atmosphere through evapotranspiration), both according to location and time of year. In January and February, the far west of Scotland is wetter, whilst in May, and August - October, much of Scotland is considerably drier, again especially in the west. Throughout the year, there is notable variation between locations, with eastern and southern areas becoming wetter and western areas becoming drier in November and December, whilst the opposite is the case in January and February.

Figure 15 - Group 2 Discussion on risks, opportunities and responses

Risks/opportunities	Anticipated impacts for natural capital (+ve or -ve).	Potential responses	Likelihood (vote)	Significance (vote)
Water scarcity may increase	Negative impacts on agriculture	Capture water in times of plenty change vegetation to be more able to retain water	High, Medium, Low, High risk	High, Medium, Low, High
Droughts increase	scarcity of water to address wildfire are less	plant locally resilient crops mulch cover plants that can grow Access and utilize local knowledge for species and plant choice	High, Medium, Low, High	High, Medium, Low, High
Flooding increase	loss of infrastructure roads, bridges, etc which will then have secondary impact destruction of local natural capital and communities	change vegetation to retain water upstream The flood being more gently with better flood plain management with better flood plain management. Lower than sea level means water can be pumped out more easily.	High, Medium, Low, High	High, Medium, Low, High
Increase in opportunity for fires to spread	increased damage to infrastructure more landscape scale fires biodiversity loss	Create fire breaks Address land ownership away from large scale owners Scholarship Sustainable forestry	High, Medium, Low, High	High, Medium, Low, High
Increased access to NC for recreation	increased GVA from tourism sector more fires started across managed forest potential for increased income in recreation tourism accommodation sector	field reversal of access code, create resilient facilities.	High, Medium, Low, High	High, Medium, Low, High
Massive increase in fuel load and reduction in its resilience	inability to deal with the fire	'fight fire with fire' - reduce fuel load, alternatively, need to upgrade 'tools' (helicopters)	High, Medium, Low, High	High, Medium, Low, High
Decrease in social capital	fewer resources to address fire	Increase place based education Address housing issue Provide access to land for food production in small parcels.	High, Medium, Low, High	High, Medium, Low, High
Reduction in inherited knowledge around how to manage land	neglect of 'traditional' management measures, so increasing fragility of systems		High, Medium, Low, High	High, Medium, Low, High
Community Ownership	increase in social capital, leading to more resilience in landscape	think and more advance, so more opportunity to develop locally appropriate solutions.	High, Medium, Low, High	High, Medium, Low, High

Figure 16 - Group 2 Discussion of wildfire risk

Overall likelihood of wildfire in Scotland (vote)	Which areas of Scotland are likely to be most affected and when?	Potential impacts	Responses
High, Medium, Low, Medium by 2045	Areas, times of year. Everywhere forests where recreational use is high Highland and Dumfries and Galloway Forestry sites in Scotland, Summer upland areas where mairburn prevalent.	Describe potential impacts huge release of CO2, post-forest state, deterioration of green space of CO2 Communities feel excluded, landscape has changed prohibitions will increase in response to incidents. Ecological damage Risk to life and property	Describe possible responses. Local food has become the norm sacrificial areas delineated education education education prohibitions increase a national high-level tiered strategy to wildfire management and mitigation Artificial rainfall in very dry season On heather moorland/peatland, low stocking density of cattle, ideally native outdoor raised, lighter weight animals along with managed mairburn so that heather does not become weed high and fire risk. Also contribute to food supply. They are part of the carbon cycle rather than hydrocarbons.

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